

ROLE OF SPIRITUAL, MORAL AND EDUCATIONAL FACTORS IN PREVENTING THE ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS

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Annotation: The article reveals the role of moral and educational factors in the prevention of environmental hazards and analyzes the relationship between ethics and law in the sphere of environmental protection and environmental education and upbringing in the prevention of environmental risks. The discourse of environmental education analyzes the role and significance of literature, art, history and religion in ensuring environmental safety, highlights their socio-philosophical aspects.

Key words: ethics, law, ecological ethics, ecological code, ecological education, ecological culture, ecological ethics in religion, principles of ecological ethics, harmony of history and nature.

Morality can be described as conceptually the sum total of a person's character and behavior. We call legal and moral laws that regulate the behavior of individuals in society. Morality is a set of rules that shape life and must be accepted by everyone in every era. In this concept of morality, which facilitates the orderly coexistence of people in the same environment and in communities, they are responsible for the natural environment in which they live." In his Address, the President emphasized the need to develop the "Environmental Code" project by October 1, 2022, involving leading international experts. The ecological code allows to regulate the field of environmental restoration and protection in the rational use of natural resources and production relations of farms and other types of enterprises operating in direct connection with the use of natural resources and negative impact on the environment in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1].

We cannot deny the Nature's need to support human life, just like "man's need for man". According to this need, he who tries to create an order over nature according to his own decisions and rules, endangers the life of nature. Schweitzer and Aldo Leopold emphasize that human relations with nature should be formed on a moral basis [2]. Leopold, who saw the concept of morality as a period between people, later connected it with air, land and water [3]. This concept of environmental ethics (ecological ethics) plays an important role in creating an order in which everyone can do this and live with a conscious conscience. Ecological ethics, a new concept for the societies of that time, began to be considered as a sub-branch of moral philosophy.

Courses in environmental philosophy and environmental ethics and academic research have been conducted in Western universities on this topic, which is rising internationally. "Environmental Ethics" is an English-language journal dealing with philosophical environmental issues. Not sensitive to these studies, Orion University of the USA published the journal "Orion University Phil Environmental Philosophy de" [4].

Instead of understanding and accepting the human-centered behavior, the concept of ecological ethics, which strengthens our relationship with nature, establishes a certain status for the animals and various creatures around us and creates a healthy foundation for future generations.

As principles of environmental ethics covered by law:

- balancing environmental protection and development activities;
- ensuring sustainable use of natural resources and protecting the rights of future generations;
- all principles are based on justice and equality;
- regulation of a person's relationship to a person, society and nature, etc.

Environmental law was added to the agenda at the Stockholm Conference in 1972 due to the development of ethical elements. The right to solidarity is included in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. It is defined as the right of people to live in a balanced and healthy environment. These rights are summarized below.

- Right to information: Plans, programs, projects and activities that have or may have a negative impact on the environment must be disclosed.
- Right to appeal: administrative court methods should be recognized to prevent, stop and remedy harm caused by filing complaints and covering urgent procedures. Criminal, legal and administrative sanctions should be applied to persons who fail to fulfill their obligations to protect ecological values and damage the environment.
- The right to participate: it is the most important tool in the exercise of these rights. This includes the right to participate in administrative activities that have a positive/negative impact on the future of the individual and society, with the exception of receiving unbiased information.
- The right to education: people of all ages and all ages have the right to environmental education [5].

Conservation of nature, emergence of ecological thinking depends on the level of environmental education and culture of the population and the young generation. Environmental legislation and decisions adopted in Uzbekistan in

the field of environmental protection and environmental education are an important step in solving this problem. In the concept of national education, special attention is paid to environmental education and upbringing of the young generation. One of the most urgent problems in the current era of globalization is environmental problems. The negative attitude of the population to the environment has led to the current problem. There is a great need for environmental education. For this, it is necessary for everyone to acquire certain environmental knowledge, to form an ecological outlook in the population, to ensure the implementation of continuous environmental education, to pay special attention to environmental education among children and students in schools and preschool educational institutions.

The purpose of ecological education is to form a sense of responsibility towards nature. Knowledge and experience gained in the process of ecological education and enlightenment lead to the emergence of ecological culture. Environmental education is a process of continuous education, upbringing and development aimed at the formation of general ecological culture and responsibility. The need for environmental education arises from the need to provide a comfortable environment for human life. Targeted environmental education is one of the main means of forming ecological culture. The correct attitude to the environment is formed as a result of ecological knowledge. Environmental attitude of a person develops his sense of environmental responsibility. Environmental education is carried out under the auspices of the United Nations Development Program.

It is of particular importance to develop cognitive activity, independent work ability in students' full understanding of the environment, in the formation of their ecological awareness and thinking, ecological worldview. After all, it is important to continuously improve the ecological culture of the young generation, as well as society, and to protect nature as a national and universal wealth. As President Sh. Mirziyoev pointed out: "The most important issue is to raise the ecological culture of the population. Of course, such problems cannot be solved only by administrative means, it can be achieved by cultivating love for mother nature in the hearts of the young generation, a sense of belonging to it" [6].

Ecological education is a morally valuable and ecologically appropriate behavior that requires the formation of an active, conscious attitude to nature. This position reflects a person's love of nature, understanding of its laws and appreciation of its beauty. Ecological education, which is a necessary factor of

harmony in the system of mutual relations between society and nature, not only helps to understand human life, but also directly participates in the formation of a well-rounded person [7].

If we want to raise our attitude to the environment to the level of modern requirements, we must have continuous (at all stages of education) environmental education. Teaching the basics of ecology in the principles of teaching is in line with the demand of the times. It is not for nothing that special attention is paid to this issue in the concept of general education of Uzbekistan (National Curriculum). Formation of ecological culture in students, careful and sensitive attitude towards the environment is the first priority.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, environmental education and upbringing were given serious attention, and its legislative base was created. Initially, environmental education was organized in three main directions:

- coverage of nature protection issues in the entire complex of academic subjects;
- professional training in the field of environmental protection and effective use of nature;
- involving students and pupils in nature protection activities on the basis of scientific research and society.

The reforms implemented in the field of education of our country, the independence of teachers at the level of state requirements, creative approach to the educational process, and the use of new technologies are of great importance in the reconstruction of education at the level of world standards. Within the framework of these reforms, there are broad prospects for the development of environmental education and the formation of an ecological worldview.

The level of environmental culture in society depends on the environmental education of the next generation, how they acquire environmental knowledge. The lack of educational programs, instructional manuals, textbooks and other manuals in schools and non-school institutions creates serious problems in the field of environmental education. Students should be able to apply the knowledge they have received in the classes in the environmental activities that they regularly participate in, in the field of study and practice, and in field experiments. The gradual development of such habits can lead to the emergence and strengthening of environmental education in them.

It is desirable to teach ecology as an independent subject at all levels of education (primary, middle and high school). There are opportunities to teach ecology in conjunction with other natural sciences.

Environmental problems have increased so much that today it is difficult to find a solution by studying them only within one discipline. Hence, certain results can be achieved by studying ecology as both a science and an integrated science. From this point of view, not only biology and geography (to a lesser extent chemistry), but also history, language and literature, physics, mathematics, informatics, art, music, labor education can provide the basics of ecology in general education schools.

It should be noted here that care for the environment in our republic has deep historical roots. These factors should be taken into account when teaching literature and history. For example, in folk literature we find a lot of information about the environment. Human-nature relations are expressed in folk proverbs, fairy tales and epics, narratives and legends, children's songs and folk rituals, verses and laments, lullabies and similes. Proverbs, which are widely used in folklore, have played an important role in shaping people's attitude to the environment since ancient times.

In Islam, certain plants and animals are designated as sacred beings. It is forbidden to harm or kill such creatures. Hunting of young wild animals and birds is prohibited. According to Sharia, their meat is haram. The abundance of such ideas in Islam has had a positive effect on the conservation of biological diversity. As a result, preservation of such animate and inanimate nature, useful plant and animal species was ensured even in the absence of nature protection laws.

In the process of formation and development for many millennia, man was not indifferent to the surrounding environment, and in his historical period, he tried to express his attitude to nature to the lovers of culture and art created by him. Archaeological excavations dating back to the first millennium BC clearly describe the views of ancient people on the environment. Archeological excavations show that in the distant past, worshiping certain animals and consecrating them as living beings was typical of ancient cultures.

Totemism, a collection of ideas about the existence of supernatural relations between man and animals or plants, existed from ancient times as a remnant of the tribal system. Most of the rock paintings in the Sarmishsay gorge of the Navoi region of our country are images of hunting. This shows that hunting was the basis of the first labor activity of people.

In the mythical way of thinking of the ancient and medieval peoples, in their still imperfect consciousness, the use of the option of consecration for the purpose of protecting nature helped to preserve environmental factors to a certain extent.

In Zoroastrianism, the sanctity option is given priority in the protection of living beings. Zoomorphic vessels and patterns on objects found in archeological excavations and reflecting the ideas of "Avesta" show that there was information about various plants and animals during the period when the worship of fire was widespread [8].

The images of Avesta deities were attached to trumpets, mouthpieces, and handles of zoomorphic vessels, which had a symbolic meaning. These figures, depicted on the skins of various animals, supposedly had a protective function. According to the "Avesta" law, animals such as cows, horses, dogs, and roosters were considered sacred and worshiped as guardians of fire.

Giving the animal a protective character and deifying it was actually a positive result of the attitude towards nature. The fire-worshippers, who associated the death of man and beast with Ahriman, considered the dead to be impure beings. This approach is one of the ways to fight against infectious diseases. Therefore, it was considered a crime to bury the dead and throw them into the water. The body was stored in special buildings or placed on a high mountain to be eaten by predators [9].

Based on the above, firstly, human influence on the environment as an anthropogenic factor exists from the earliest times of his interaction with nature. Air, soil and water pollution is one of the main environmental problems of our time. Secondly, organizing ecology lessons in secondary schools, teaching ecology as a separate subject, increasing environmental topics from chemistry and physics, including environmental questions among other subjects in graduation and entrance exams, establishing an "Ecology" cabinet together with other science cabinets. We also believe that it is necessary to study ecology in integration with other subjects in general education schools. We envisage compulsory teaching of ecology at all levels of vocational education, secondary special and higher educational institutions, regardless of specialization.

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